

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Some Aldopentoses by Quinquevalent Vanadium in Sulphuric Acid

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The oxidation of D-xylose, L-arabinose and D-ribose by quinquevalent vanadium in sulphuric acid medium has been found to be of first order with respect to both oxidant and substrate concentrations. The rate of oxidation has been found to increase with first power of $[H^+]$ in 2.0M to 4.5M acid concentration range and with second power of $[H^+]$ in higher acid range $>4.5M$ at constant HSO_4^- concentration. The increase in oxidation rate with HSO_4^- concentration at constant H^+ concentration has been also observed. The thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated from Arrhenius plots. The effect of changing the composition of acetic acid-water binary mixture on rate has indicated the reaction to be ion-dipole type. Possible reaction steps have been also proposed.

KINETICS of oxidation of carbohydrates, mainly of hexoses has been studied by various oxidants, including the ions of higher valent transition metals like Ce(IV)^{1,2,3}, Co(III)⁴, Mn(III)⁵. In comparison of hexoses, the kinetics of oxidation of pentoses, which constitute an important category of monosaccharides has been studied by few oxidants like Br_2 water in alkaline medium⁶, chloramine-T⁷, Cu(II) in alkaline medium⁸, Ag(I) in alkaline medium⁹. Amongst the various transition metal ions used for oxidation studies, quinquevalent vanadium in acid medium is a most versatile and potent oxidant and has been used for oxidation studies of various organic compounds¹⁰ including hexoses¹¹. The present work deals with the oxidation of some aldopentoses like D-xylose, L-arabinose and D-ribose by quinquevalent vanadium to evaluate the general feature of oxidation process in sulphuric acid medium and steps involved in it.

Experimental

Vanadium (V) solution was prepared by dissolving ammonium meta vanadate (Reidel) in appropriate concentration of sulphuric acid (Analar/B.D.H.). Solutions of aldopentoses (E. Merck/B.D.H.) were prepared fresh daily. Other various chemicals used like sodium bisulphate, sodium sulphate, acetic acid N-phenyl anthranilic acid, chromotropic acid etc. were of Analar/B.D.H. grade.

Oxidation reactions were followed by quenching aliquots withdrawn at regular known interval of time in ice cold titration flask containing 5 ml. of 5N sulphuric

acid and estimating unreacted vanadium(V) with a standard solution of Mohr's salt using N-phenyl anthranilic acid as an indicator.

Results

All the three aldopentoses consumed ~ 2 equivalents of vanadium (V) in 3.5 M sulphuric acid in 24 hours at 40° under the condition of kinetic run. The reaction can be represented stoichiometrically by equation (1)

In presence of excess of vanadium (V) (~ 20 folds), it was found that one equivalent of aldopentose required ten equivalents of vanadium (V) for complete oxidation (~ 10 days) in each case. Thus, the overall oxidation reaction can be represented by equation (2)

The formation of HCHO as intermediate product was confirmed with usual tests and with chromotropic acid spot test also.^{12(a)} After the completion of reaction the formation of HCOOH was also confirmed by mercuric chloride and chromotropic acid spot test^{12(b)}. The formation of free radicals during the course of reaction was confirmed by the induced polymerisation reaction of acrylyn-H monomer (Asian Acrylates, Bombay).

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANT WITH ALDOPENTOSE CONCENTRATION

- A. [Vanadium(V)]= 1.0×10^{-2} M, [H₂SO₄]=3.5 M, Temp.=45°
 B. [Vanadium(V)]= 1.0×10^{-2} M, [H₂SO₄]=3.5 M, Temp.=40°
 C. [Vanadium(V)]= 1.0×10^{-2} M, [H₂SO₄]=3.5 M, Temp.=40°

[Aldopentose] M × 10	A		B		C	
	$10^4 k_1$ s ⁻¹	$10^4 k_1 / [D\text{-xylose}]$ l mole ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$10^4 k_1$ s ⁻¹	$10^4 k_1 / [D\text{-arabinose}]$ l mole ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$10^4 k_1$ s ⁻¹	$10^4 k_1 / [D\text{-ribose}]$ l mole ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
1.0	1.38	13.80	0.69	6.90	0.97	9.70
2.0	2.57	12.85	1.37	6.85	1.91	9.55
3.0	4.34	14.46	1.89	6.30	3.13	10.43
4.0	5.26	13.15	2.54	6.35	3.83	9.57
5.0	6.69	13.38	3.30	6.60	5.00	10.00
6.0	8.13	13.55	3.85	6.42	—	—

Ave. $\frac{10^4 k_1}{[D\text{-xylose}]} = 13.53 \pm 0.40$ Ave. $\frac{10^4 k_1}{[L\text{-arabinose}]} = 6.57 \pm 0.21$ Ave. $\frac{10^4 k_1}{[D\text{-ribose}]} = 9.85 \pm 0.29$

The kinetic studies were performed by taking aldopentose and sulphuric acid in sufficient excess over the vanadium (V) concentration. It was observed that the rate of disappearance of vanadium (V) followed first order kinetics uniformly. The pseudo first order rate constants (k_1) were evaluated from the integrated form of first order rate equation. The order with respect to aldopentose has been also found to be one (Table 1). Further, linear graphs passing through origin can be obtained if drawn between $1/k_1$ and $1/[\text{aldopentose}]$ showing no kinetic evidence for intermediate compound formation between vanadium (V) and aldopentose.

In preliminary studies rate constant has been found to increase exponentially with sulphuric acid concentration and activity computed from activity coefficient data¹³ (Table 2). For finding out the dependence of rate constant on H⁺ concentration at constant [HSO₄⁻] and on HSO₄⁻ concentration at constant [H⁺], the rate studies were performed in two different H⁺ concentration ranges. In lower H⁺ concentration range (2.0 M to 4.5 M) the rate constant has been found to depend on first power of H⁺ concentration, whereas in higher H⁺ concentration, range (5.0 M to 8.0 M) a second power dependence on [H⁺] has been observed (Table 3). Further, an increase in rate constant with HSO₄⁻ concentration has been also observed in both acid ranges (Table 4).

From the data given in Table 3 linear graphs with negative slope values can be obtained if drawn between $\log k_1$ and H₀ (values taken from Paul and Long's

Table¹⁴) in all the three cases and in two different ranges. Further, from the linear plots obtained between $\log k_1 + H_0$ and $\log a_{H_2O}^{15}$ "ω" values have been computed as 8.0, 7.0 and 7.0 in lower acid concentration range and 3.0, 3.2 and 2.8 in higher acid concentration range for D-xylose, L-arabinose and D-ribose respectively.

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF RATE CONSTANT ON SULPHURIC ACID CONCENTRATION

- A [Vanadium(V)]= 1.0×10^{-2} M,
[D-xylose]= 1.0×10^{-1} M [Temp.=40°
 B [Vanadium(V)]= 1.0×10^{-2} M,
[L-arabinose]= 1.0×10^{-1} M Temp.=40°
 C [Vanadium(V)]= 1.0×10^{-2} M,
[D-ribose]= 1.0×10^{-1} M Temp.=40°

[H ₂ SO ₄] M	a ±	A $10^4 k_1$ s ⁻¹	B $10^4 k_1$ s ⁻¹	C $10^4 k_1$ s ⁻¹
2.0	0.21	0.56	0.38	0.65
3.0	0.35	0.81	0.53	1.02
4.0	0.67	1.12	0.72	1.62
5.0	0.84	1.94	1.27	2.45
6.0	1.23	2.55	1.89	5.26
8.0	2.27	7.21	4.83	12.10

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF RATE CONSTANT ON H⁺ CONCENTRATION AT CONSTANT [HSO₄⁻]

Lower range

A [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[D-xylose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [HSO₄⁻] = 4.5 M ; Temp. = 45°

B [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[L-arabinose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [HSO₄⁻] = 4.5 M ; Temp. = 40°

C [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[D-ribose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [HSO₄⁻] = 4.5 M ; Temp. = 40°

[H ⁺] M	A 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹	B 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹	C 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹
2.0	0.86	—	—
2.5	1.06	0.48	0.69
3.0	1.26	0.56	0.82
3.5	1.47	0.62	0.96
4.0	2.10	0.72	1.12
4.5	2.44	0.88	1.26

Higher range

A [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[D-xylose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [HSO₄⁻] = 8.0 M ; Temp. = 34°

B [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[L-arabinose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [HSO₄⁻] = 8.0 M ; Temp. = 35°

C [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[D-ribose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [HSO₄⁻] = 8.0 M ; Temp. = 35°

[H ⁺] M	A 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹	B 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹	C 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹
5.0	0.49	0.66	1.04
6.0	0.84	0.78	1.55
7.0	1.08	1.13	2.09
8.0	1.52	1.45	2.53

It has been also observed that rate constant increases inversely with dielectric constant of medium varied by taking binary mixtures of acetic acid-water of different compositions (Table 5). The dielectric constants of such mixtures have been computed by assuming approximate validity of mixture law¹⁶ at the temperature of study.

A linear plot if drawn between log k₁ and 1/D can be obtained with a positive slope showing the reaction under study to be of ion dipole type. It can be assumed that aldopentose molecule behaves as dipole in aqueous medium whereas positive ionic species of vanadium (V) can be considered to be active in the reaction.

TABLE 4—DEPENDENCE OF RATE CONSTANT ON HSO₄⁻ CONCENTRATION AT CONSTANT [H⁺]

Lower range

A [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[D-xylose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [H⁺] = 3.5 M ; Temp. = 45°

B [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[L-arabinose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [H⁺] = 3.5 M ; Temp. = 40°

C [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M [H⁺] = 3.5 M
[D-ribose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M ; Temp. = 40°

[HSO ₄ ⁻] M	A 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹	B 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹	C 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹
3.5	1.25	0.69	1.07
4.0	1.37	0.82	1.24
4.5	1.59	0.99	1.44
5.0	1.80	—	—
5.5	1.92	1.28	1.74

Higher range

A [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[D-xylose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [H⁺] = 6.0 M ; Temp. = 35°

B [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[L-arabinose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [H⁺] = 6.0 M ; Temp. = 35°

C [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[D-ribose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [H⁺] = 6.0 M ; Temp. = 35°

[HSO ₄ ⁻] M	A 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹	B 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹	C 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹
6.0	0.81	0.63	1.69
6.5	0.97	0.82	2.20
7.0	1.29	0.96	2.63
8.0	1.84	1.27	3.30

TABLE 5—DEPENDENCE OF RATE CONSTANT ON ACETIC ACID-WATER COMPOSITION

A [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[D-xylose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [H₂SO₄] = 1.81 M ; Temp. = 40°

B [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[L-arabinose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [H₂SO₄] = 1.35 M ; Temp. = 40°

C [Vanadium(V)] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[D-ribose] = 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M [H₂SO₄] = 1.61 M ; Temp. = 40°

Acetic acid %	10 ³ D	A 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹	B 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹	C 10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹
30	18.81	1.45	1.26	1.23
40	21.53	2.66	2.34	2.34
50	25.17	4.59	3.84	4.72
60	30.36	10.94	7.31	8.90
70	38.04	30.66	19.88	22.23

TABLE 6—DEPENDENCE OF RATE CONSTANT ON TEMPERATURE

A [Vanadium(V)]= 1.0×10^{-2} M [D-xylose]= 1.0×10^{-1} M [H_2SO_4]=3.5 M
 B [Vanadium(V)]= 1.0×10^{-2} M [L-arabinose]= 1.0×10^{-1} M [H_2SO_4]=3.5 M
 C [Vanadium(V)]= 1.0×10^{-2} M [D-ribose]= 1.0×10^{-1} M [H_2SO_4]=3.5 M

	35°	40°	$10^4 \times k_1/s^{-1}$			$\frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{K. cal. mole^{-1}}$	$\frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{e.u.}$	$\frac{\Delta G^\ddagger \text{ at } 313^\circ K}{K. cal./mole}$
			45°	50°	55°			
A	0.45	0.53	1.40	1.93	4.23	21.46	-6.63	23.53
B	0.44	0.67	1.24	2.23	3.72	22.80	-2.44	23.50
C	0.68	0.98	1.98	3.21	5.31	20.79	-8.04	23.25

Many earlier studies^{17,18,19,20} have indicated that the form of the vanadium(V) active species depend on acid types and their concentration ranges. If VO_2^+ is considered as an initial species of vanadium(V) in acidic medium, then from the dependence of rate constant on $[H^+]$ and increase in rate constant with $[HSO_4^-]$ in lower acid concentration range ($\leq 4.5M$), the active species of vanadium(V) in this range can be designated by considering the following equilibria^{17,21,22}

Similarly from the results obtained in higher acid concentration range ($>4.5M$) the following equilibria can be considered to be operative²³ for the formation of active species in this range

The data on dependence of rate constant on temperature has been summarised in Table 6. The activation parameters evaluated from Arrhenius plots have also been given.

A linear isokinetic plot with β value $340^\circ K$ can be obtained if drawn between $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$, showing that the oxidation reaction under study is both energy and entropy controlled obeying Leffler's compensation law²⁴. Hence, an identical oxidation mechanism for D-xylose, L-arabinose and D-ribose can be proposed.

Vanadium(V) is present in two cases, that is, in lower and higher acid concentration range as A and B shown in equation 3 and 4 and hence the first step of oxidation can be shown either as 5(a) or(b).

or in general

where $R^\cdot$ is $CHO.CHOH.CHOH.CHOH^\cdot$

The free radical $CHO.CHOH.CHOH.CHOH^\cdot$ thus formed breaks further in a chain mechanism to formic acid and formaldehyde as :

The formaldehyde formed in steps (5) and (6) can further be oxidised to formic acid, if excess of oxidant is present as follows:

The above proposed steps of oxidation mechanism incorporate the results obtained during the studies.

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